

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 957781.

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GRANT AGREEMENT NUMBER 957781

WP3 – Consumer engagement methodology definition and activity coordination D3.5 – Report on citizen recruitment activity outcome

Responsible organisation	GECO
Contributing organisation(s)	ESR,CERTH,Hypertech,Mytilineos, AEM, LaSolar, MIW, RINA
Due date of Deliverable	31/10/2021
Actual date of submission	29/10/2021
Type of deliverable	Report
Dissemination level	Public

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Version history

Version	Date	Comments
ToC	16.07.21	Draft ToC
Draft v1	13.10.21	
1.0	29.10.21	Final version

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

As part of the demonstration and living lab (LL) activities, commercial and residential end-customers will be engaged to gather feedback, test and implement the ACCEPT solutions. The aim is to directly engage at least 770 citizens as participants across the four pilot countries. Citizen recruitment was done primarily through the ex-ante surveys conducted as part of task T6.1 in WP6. In addition, interactions with citizens have already begun, and good progress has been made with regard to further recruitment across all four pilot sites.

In the Greek pilot, the recruitment goal is a public football stadium and 63 local residences. Currently, 63 potential users have been identified and are currently being assessed for their suitability. A workshop designed to raise awareness of the ACCEPT project and build trust with potential end-users took place in M7. Currently, 63 different prospective pilot users have expressed interest in participating in the project.

In the Spanish pilot, the recruitment goal is to involve 50 citizens in piloting activities, of which, 15 will be prosumers. Following the initial recruitment process, 54 residential users and 18 prosumers have been identified and are being reviewed to select the final participants who will take part in ACCEPT. A video telco and various correspondences were also undertaken with the goal of recruitment (i.e. instilling confidence in the project with citizens, and opening communication channels with the public.)

In the Dutch pilot, the aim is to recruit 50 households and 1 business company. Thus far, awareness has been raised in the community through various communication materials. 40 households with assets of interest to the project have been identified and communication with these end-users has been initiated.

The Swiss pilot consists of two separate areas, the Arena Innovation Community (AIC) which consist of a residential area in the suburbs of Lugano and Fondazione La Sosta (FLS), an elderly care home within the urban area. The recruitment objectives were to engage with all the residential users (approximately 50 users, one per house), the 4 building owners and the 2 utility managers in the AIC. For the FLS, all 30 users and the management of the elderly care home are targeted. Engagement activities thus far have included information letters, a workshop and one-to-one communication with 63 members of the community. With regards to the recruitment progress, 50 have signed the agreement with the energy community and it is expected that all citizens will have been engaged by M11.

With regards to the recruitment activities undertaken as part of the LL activities, citizens which included consumers and prosumers in each pilot community were engaged to provide feedback on the ACCEPT use cases through concept surveys. 115 end-users in total were engaged, 38 in Greece, 35 in Spain, 23 in Switzerland and 19 in the Netherlands. Engagements with these end-users were facilitated through collaboration with WP9 through the creation of communication materials which enables the process of building trust and a collaborative relationship between pilot leaders and local communities. Combined

Table 1. ACCEPT citizen recruitment as of M10

	Recruitment	
	<i>Ex-ante survey (WP6)</i>	<i>Living Lab activities (WP2)</i>
Greece	61	39
Spain	55	44
Switzerland	64	28
Netherlands	40	22
TOTAL	220	133

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ACRONYMS

AIC	Arena Innovation Community
LL	Living Lab
FLS	Fondazione la Sosta

1. Introduction

1.1. Scope and objectives of task

This deliverable will provide details on the ACCEPT citizen recruitment efforts up to M10. The processes and results of the recruitment have been expanded upon as they relate to the living lab, community mapping, and co-creation activities.

1.2. Structure of deliverable

The deliverable structure will follow the below structure:

- Chapter 2 outlines the high-level recruitment goals of the project and the activities included in the approach to citizen recruitment.
- Chapter 3 presents the recruitment activities and results of each pilot site.
- Chapter 4 describes the next steps for the citizen recruitment activities.
- Chapter 5 presents a summary and evaluation of the recruitment activities carried out thus far in the project and links the achievements to other objectives in the project.

1.3. Interdependencies with other tasks and deliverables

The recruitment and preliminary selection of candidate participants were carried out under the framework of the ex-ante pilot surveys conducted in task T6.1 of WP6. The LL activities and citizen engagement also contributed to the citizen recruitment at pilot sites. The materials used for communication in the pilot site recruitment activities were developed through WP9. The results presented here are linked with other deliverables connected with the LL, community mapping, and co-creation activities reported in D3.2, D3.7 and D7.1, respectively. The activities and outreach links to the LL objectives in WP3 for task T3.1, how the recruitment related activities contributed to T3.1 objectives are referred to in the subsections of chapter 3, which describe the pilot specific activities.

Figure 1 Interdependencies of D3.5

2. ACCEPT's approach to recruitment

The ACCEPT demonstration activities aim to directly engage more than 770 citizens as participants across the four pilot countries. The engagements will be geared towards the use cases developed for the ACCEPT solution. A multitude of factors has contributed to the citizen recruitment that has taken place up to M10. This chapter will explain different tasks and work packages contributed to the approach in ACCEPT for citizen recruitment, specific details of the application of these activities as well as results from each pilot's recruitment efforts will be presented in the subsequent chapters.

2.1. Concept survey (T2.1: WP2)

In the framework of the WP2 activities, specifically task 2.1 related to users' requirements, use cases and business cases, the pilot partners were engaged to collect feedback on end-user requirements. Two surveys were created to reach business and customer end-users. Both customer and business stakeholders that are involved in each of the four pilots were engaged through the survey to promote awareness and knowledge and collect feedback on how the ACCEPT solutions to be developed and understand the perspective and potential concerns related to the ACCEPT services. It was important to approach both business and customer users to understand both the citizen and business perspectives with regards to interest and knowledge on energy communities. The surveys used for task T2.1 were distributed to local stakeholders by the respective pilot partners in the ACCEPT consortium. The survey targeted towards business users was distributed by email to the local stakeholders and the survey targeted at customers was distributed through email, individual interviews, phone calls and in-person workshops (method of approach varied between pilot sites, see chapter 3 for more details).

2.2. Ex-ante survey (T6.1: WP6)

The ex-ante survey carried out in T6.1 (and T2.1) raised awareness on services offered through the project and allowed candidate participants to sign up to be part of ACCEPT. Following the collection of responses in the ex-ante survey, audits have been carried out for ensuring the eligibility of citizens and compliance with technical requirements. All pilot partners have completed the Level 1 surveys for candidate prosumers. The results of these surveys have been analysed at a high level by the technical coordination team to assess the eligibility of prosumers to take part in the project. Following the level 1 survey results, pilot partners are provided with a list of eligible prosumers for whom the Level 2 surveys will need to be completed. The subsections of chapter 3 in this deliverable will report on the results of the ex-ante survey for each pilot.

2.3. Outreach activities for impact enhancement (WP9)

Through WP9, several communication materials were created to raise awareness, knowledge and engagement in citizens and maximise the efficacy of the outreach and potential recruitment of citizens to the ACCEPT project. Content that was created included project leaflets and posters which explained the high-level goals, services and benefits of ACCEPT, pilot specific brochures were created that detailed unique aspects of each pilot site in the context of ACCEPT and several social media channels were utilised to promote ACCEPT. The material produced through WP9 activities was integral for disseminating the ACCEPT solution and the recruitment of pilot citizens.

2.4. Living Lab activities and collaboration (T3.1: WP3)

The concept survey carried out as part of task T2.1 was undertaken as part of the LL activities in T3.1. During the survey preparation stage, the aims and content of the surveys to be deployed in each pilot site were discussed and refined through an iterative process involving RINA-C, GECO-Global (responsible for the LL activities in WP3) and the pilot partners (AEM, Mytilineos, LaSolar and ESR). The recruitment efforts have been built on the foundation of close collaboration with pilot partners and task leaders in the ACCEPT consortium. The pilot partner's involvement in this process was essential as they are the ones with direct contact with end-users.

2.5. Barriers to recruitment

There were some restrictions to the recruitment process related to COVID-19. In some cases, physical workshops were not possible for administering the surveys in WP2 and WP6. Therefore, various remote-based methodologies were used for gathering feedback for the respective surveys. In addition to the impact of COVID-19 on collecting feedback for the surveys, part of the recruitment process involves carrying out technical audits at citizen premises. Restrictions to accessing such premises due to COVID-19 concerns or measures could introduce risks around such

activities. Other issues and the effect of COVID-19 for the specific pilots will be discussed in the sub-sections of chapter 3. Another issue encountered was the variable level of involvement and knowledge of the citizens. In some pilots, citizens were deeply involved in an energy community before the ACCEPT project, whereas in other pilots, topics around energy communities were less recognized. This problem was easily mitigated by ensuring the right amount of information was given to the user based on their current knowledge level. This is an important point for any future recruitment and engagement activities carried out as part of ACCEPT.

3. Pilot citizen recruitment

This chapter details the application of the methodology explained in chapter two for citizen recruitment in each pilot region. For each pilot site, details will be provided on:

- The citizen recruitment goals
- The citizen engagement activities conducted, focussing on communication materials (WP9), concept surveys (WP2) and ex-ante surveys (WP6)
- Citizen recruitment achievements, focussing on results from the ex-ante surveys, concept testing surveys and engagement activities which link to the objectives in the LL activities as part of task T3.1
- Barriers encountered in the recruitment process, focussing on COVID-19 restrictions

3.1. Aspra Spitia Community, Greece

3.1.1. Recruitment goals

The goal of the Greek pilot site in Aspra Spitia is the implementation of the ACCEPT solution in a public football stadium and 63 local residences. This initial target may require adjustment to align with the technical specifications and needs of the project as some cases may not sufficiently match the profile of the candidate participants. Mytilineos has collected a pool of 63 candidates, 61 of which have completed the questionnaire. The facility management team of Aspra Spitia has begun auditing the suitability of these candidates in order to make the final selection.

3.1.2. Recruitment engagement activities

With regards to activities undertaken thus far, on July 19th, 2021, in the open-air summer cinema hall in Aspra Spitia, the first workshop for the Greek pilot site of the ACCEPT project was conducted to raise awareness with prospective pilot users. The workshop was primarily hosted by the facility management team of Aspra Spitia alongside the dedicated European projects team of Mytilineos and Hypertech (the ACCEPT project management team). The workshop included a presentation and an open discussion which allowed the presentation team to answer questions and clarify any possible concerns of the prospective pilot participants. Hypertech and Mytilineos also delivered a presentation that provided a high-level description of the project, the main objectives of the implementation of the ACCEPT solutions and the expected results and benefits. The presentation also provided details of technical specifications, including a description of the required equipment for the project's needs. During the event, communication materials created in WP9 were administered to attendees, such as information leaflets, the concept and ex-ante surveys created as part of WP2 and WP3, respectively, and even participation gifts (pens & keychains with charging plugs for portable devices). Social media communication was also undertaken around the event. The success of the event was evident from the interest expressed by the participants following the presentation. As a result, we were able to start building a trustful relationship with the pilot users while receiving constructive feedback on their needs, thoughts, perspectives and expectations, allowing us to cooperate even more effectively in the future.

To continue active citizen engagement, Mytilineos intends to select some of the citizens from the pilot site with which bi-annual workshops can be organized to get more feedback and discuss citizen concerns or thoughts that arise during the ACCEPT project development. These workshops can be in large or small groups or on an individual one-to-one session, depending on the needs of participants and the type of feedback required. As well as these follow-up events, an additional goal for the Greek pilot is to consistently produce communication materials (photos, interviews, etc.) to regularly inform the citizens outside of the project on news and developments around the ACCEPT solution and energy transition via our social media channels.

3.1.3. Recruitment achievements

Thus far in the Greek pilot, 100 citizens have been directly engaged through a variety of engagement activities including a workshop, a presentation and an open discussion session (see Table 2).

Table 2 Greek pilot site citizen recruitment and LL engagement achievements

Concept survey responses	Business user: 1 Citizen user: 38
Ex-ante survey respondents	Total responses: 61 Eligible for pilot participation: 61
Citizen engagement activities	Workshop Open discussion Presentation introducing ACCEPT

3.1.4. Recruitment barriers

COVID-19 did not create any significant obstacles or limitations in the recruitment activities undertaken as part of the ACCEPT project so far. However, it may cause some issues in future, for example, face-to-face communication with the prospective pilot citizens may not be possible. Therefore, interactions may be restricted to email, telephone calls, virtual calls, or in large open spaces in accordance with social distancing guidelines related to COVID-19.

3.2. Renewable Energy Cooperative Buildings, Spain

3.2.1. Recruitment goals

The goal of the Spanish demonstration is to involve 50 citizens in the piloting activities, 15 of which will be citizens who both consume and produce energy (prosumers). After the initial recruitment process, 54 homes and 18 prosumers have been pre-selected and are under eligibility assessment (based on a set of technical criteria relating to the household appliances/equipment) to be selected as the final participant group who will take part in ACCEPT.

3.2.2. Recruitment engagement activities

All activities undertaken thus far in terms of engagement have been done through phone calls, emails and telcos. No presentations or workshops have yet taken place due to restrictions related to COVID-19. La Solar Energia is a users and consumers cooperative non-profit and has focused engagement activities on members of the cooperative, currently 261 citizens, as they have a full preference and commitment with La Solar Energia's objectives. These members have paid a subscription fee and have the right to participate and vote at general assemblies. All citizens contacted thus far had previous knowledge of the ACCEPT project, as they were informed of the high-level objectives through La Solar Energia's regular newsletter. The first contact with citizens took place on June 7th, 2021 through email correspondent which explained the high-level objectives of the project, preliminary requirements and needs, and the offer to participate in ACCEPT. In addition, an invitation to a video telco was also offered as a response to doubts being raised by some members. The video telco took place on the 11th of June during which a general review of the project was presented along with a Q&A session to alleviate citizen concerns.

All participants interested in participating in ACCEPT were interviewed via a telephone call. This allowed La Solar Energia to resolve any potential doubt from the user and filter users who did not meet the minimum requirements. If more participants, or specifically more prosumers, are needed, another search will be performed, and if necessary, customers from the cooperative will be considered. The main goal of this process was the reinforcement of members confidence in our project, the enhancement of existing members' previous knowledge of the electric system and building a good team relationship together with MIWenergia.

3.2.3. Recruitment achievements

Thus far in the Spanish pilot, 90 citizens have been directly engaged on a one-to-one level through a variety of calls and emails. An open discussion was also conducted via a video telco (see Table 3).

Table 3 Spanish pilot site citizen recruitment and LL engagement achievements

Concept survey responses	Business user: 9 Citizen user: 35
Ex-ante survey respondents	Total responses: 55 Eligible for pilot participation: 46
Citizen engagement activities	One-to-one communication (telephone calls and face-to-face) Open discussion

3.2.4. Recruitment barriers

Despite the inability to do face-to-face meetings, the impact of COVID-19 has been relatively small at this stage, as digital tools, emails and phone calls have been sufficient for all activities thus far. No general meetings are planned at this moment, and the first visits to participants' dwellings are expected to be done with minimum restrictions.

3.3. Eva Lanxmeer Community, Netherlands

3.3.1. Recruitment goals

The goal for the Dutch pilot is to connect to 50 households and 1 business company.

3.3.2. Recruitment engagement activities

Thus far, leaflets describing the project overview and high-level goals have been distributed to all 300 households in the pilot community. Furthermore, an article that described the goals and services of the project has been published in a local magazine and issued to the community. The article also included details on how households can participate in ACCEPT. As the magazine is published four times a year, future articles on the ACCEPT project can also be published. To increase the number of participants, households with assets that are interesting for the project were identified and efforts have begun to contact these households through telephone calls. Currently, 40 registrations have been confirmed via these phone calls. Assessment is currently in progress to identify if these 40 households possess assets that can be part of the project.

Through the community outreach described above, the awareness within the whole community regarding the goals and innovation of ACCEPT has been raised and the initial stages of relationship-building have begun. The participants contacted thus far expressed that they feel they can be active participants in the transformation and sustainability efforts which previously they considered as restricted to being influenced only by major corporations.

3.3.3. Recruitment achievements

Thus far in the Dutch pilot, 52 citizens have been directly engaged on a one-to-one level (see Table 4).

Table 4 Dutch pilot site citizen recruitment and LL engagement achievements

Concept survey responses	Business user: 3 Citizen user: 19
Ex-ante survey respondents	Total responses: 40 Eligible for pilot participation: 17
Citizen engagement activities	One-to-one communication (telephone calls and face-to-face)

3.3.4. Recruitment barriers

The recruitment of citizens in the Dutch pilot region was not significantly hindered by COVID-19 restrictions. At the time when recruitment activities were initiated, most Covid-19 related restrictions in the Netherlands had been lifted.

3.4. Arena Innovation Community & Fondazione la Sosta, Switzerland

3.4.1. Recruitment goals

The AEM pilot site in Switzerland consists of the Arena Innovation Community (AIC), which represents a residential area in the suburbs of Lugano and the Fondazione la Sosta (FLS), an elderly care home within the urban area. Recruitment activities were conducted separately for these two areas. The recruitment objectives of AEM consist of engaging with all the residential citizens (approximately 50, one per house), 4 building owners and the 2 utility managers of the Arena Innovation Community. For the FLS, all 30 users and the management of the elderly care home are targeted. All citizens (86 in total) would be required to sign an agreement to participate in the energy community. As of M10, AEM has reached out to all utility managers, city officials, and building owners. In terms of citizen engagement, 50 have signed the agreement with the energy community. It is expected that citizen engagement will have reached the target number by M11.

3.4.2. Recruitment engagement activities

To achieve the recruitment goals, there has been a focussed effort to involve the utility administrators and municipality at an early stage. The aim is to get all necessary stakeholders on board to develop the energy community. Outreach has begun in the form of an information letter which was sent to all citizens. This letter explained the challenges of the energy transition and the importance of innovation projects such as ACCEPT to address these challenges. The early stakeholder involvement also included reaching out to building owners to obtain consent to contact tenants. With the support of the building owners, AEM sent an invitation letter requesting attendance to three workshops, one of the workshops has since been carried out. During the workshop, AEM presented the motivation and goals of the ACCEPT project and the practical steps for implementation. As part of the workshop, a Q&A session took place to discuss thoughts and concerns raised by the potential participants. The more sceptical citizens were approached following the discussion to discuss the benefits of participating in the energy Community. In addition to the workshop, AEM also held one-to-one meetings with approximately 60 citizens.

Overall, awareness of the energy transition and its challenges has increased significantly. Many discussions were initiated by citizens during the workshops as well as during the one-to-one meetings and follow-up phone calls. Some users even visited the AEM office to get more information. This positive response to the workshop enforces the need for repeat workshops for other citizens in the future.

3.4.3. Recruitment achievements

Thus far in the Swiss pilot, 92 citizens have been directly engaged through workshops, discussions and on a one-to-one level through a variety of calls and face-to-face meetings (see Table 3).

Table 5 Swiss pilot site citizen recruitment and LL engagement achievements

Concept survey responses	Business user: 5 Citizen user: 23
Ex-ante survey respondents	Total responses: 64 Eligible for pilot participation: 52
Citizen engagement activities	Workshop Q&A Discussion One-to-one communication (telephone calls and face-to-face)

3.4.4. Recruitment barriers

The restrictions encountered thus far related to COVID-19 were relatively minimal. Due to the pandemic, the workshop had to be carried out later than initially planned, and it is possible that attendance was reduced due to medical safety measures, such as being required to wear masks or contact tracing procedures. To reduce the risk, AEM postponed the workshop to a more favourable period (when cases of COVID-19 were reduced) and limited the number of participants per workshop. In addition to the issues related to COVID-19, it was also apparent that summertime was not the ideal period for conducting recruitment activities as many users were on vacation. This is something to consider for future engagement with citizens.

4. Next steps

The initial work towards engaging and recruiting citizens will need to be built on to increase participation and continue co-creation with local citizens. To this end, a results 'share-back' activity is planned for M11 for the concept survey that was conducted as part of T2.1 (and as part of the LL work in T3.1). The goal of this is to inform the citizens of the results of the concept survey and provide a high-level description of how their responses helped to develop the ACCEPT service. This engagement activity aims to build trust through transparency and promote a collaborative attitude between the citizens and ACCEPT project consortium. Several other engagement activities have also been planned as part of the co-creation efforts in T3.1. Table 6 displays the engagement roadmap for the ACCEPT project. As shown in the table, many engagements are planned with a variety of stakeholders (note, the engagements listed in Table 6 are subject to change depending on project developments).

Table 6. ACCEPT engagement roadmap

Timeline	Stakeholders	Description	Activity	Related tasks
Stage 1: User requirements exploration				
M6	External & internal	Collection of market actor and prosumer requirements	Concept test survey	T2.1
M10	Internal	Feedback per pilot site on Business Cases-Use Cases-System Architecture and Measurement & Verification Methodology	Survey	T2.2, T2.3
M10-12	External	ACCEPT community member concept test results share back	One page newsletter or community presentation	T3.1
M12-15	External & internal	Feedback on Service Level Agreements and contract terms for the business models and services	TBD	T2.5
Stage 2: Prototyping validation				
M10-13	External & internal	Participation in ex-ante pilot surveys	Audit	T6.1
M11-12	External	ACCEPT introduction for community members	One page newsletter or community presentation	T3.1, T7.1
M13-14	External	ACCEPT persona validation workshop	4 workshops (one/pilot)	T3.1, T3.4
M15-16	External & internal	Co-creation workshop 1: Feedback on ACCEPT system 1 st prototype	4 workshops (one/pilot)	T7.1, T6.2, WP4, WP5
M16-M18	External	Community co-creation shareback: Highlevel insights from 1 st prototype co-creation workshop	One page newsletter or community presentation	T7.1
M18-M21	Internal	Feedback of pre-validation results	TBD	T6.4

M20-24 M15-M23	External	Scheduling of installation activities and training of pilot participants	TBD	T6.5, T6.6
M26-27	External & internal	Co-creation workshop 2: Feedback on ACCEPT system 2 nd prototype	4 workshops (one/pilot)	T7.1, T6.2, WP4, WP5, WP7, WP8
M28-M30	External	Community co-creation shareback: Highlevel insights from 2 nd prototype co-creation workshop	One page newsletter or community presentation	T7.1
M35-36	External & internal	Co-creation workshop 3: Feedback on ACCEPT system final prototype	4 workshops (one/pilot)	T7.1, T6.2, WP7, WP8
M37-M39	External	Community co-creation shareback: Highlevel insights from 3 rd prototype co-creation workshop	One page newsletter or community presentation	T7.1
Stage 3: Business modelling validation				
M27-M33	External & internal	Feedback on obstacles for DR application in energy communities	TBD	T8.1
M37-40	External	Feedback on business models	TBD	T8.4
M37-M42	External	Feedback on exploitable results & business potential	TBD	T8.2

With regards to the ex-ante survey carried out in T6.1, following analysis of potential participants who completed the initial Level 1 survey, a Level 2 survey will be issued to those deemed eligible at a high level to take part in ACCEPT project. The analysis of the Level 2 surveys will determine the full eligibility of prosumers to participate in the project. Level 2 surveys are anticipated to be completed and ready for assessment by M12. After the Level 2 survey assessment, pilot partners will be provided with the list of project participants that meet the technical requirements and a list of equipment for each participant that will need to be installed at citizen premises for their participation in the trials.

In addition to the continued efforts towards the surveys in T6.1 and the LL engagement activities in T3.1, communication and outreach will continue in WP9. Through social media updates, the website and various other channels of communication, the ACCEPT project will continue to be promoted to raise awareness of citizens. The continued exposure of ACCEPT will optimise the recruitment and engagement of pilot citizens.

5. Conclusion

As highlighted in Chapter 3, pilot citizens have been contacted and engaged through various activities and communication channels. The target in ACCEPT is to engage with 770 citizens, 353 citizens have already been engaged via workshops, discussion groups, presentations and meetings. This means that by M10 of the project, progress towards the target KPI of engaging 770 citizens stands at 46%. Considering the upcoming engagement activities highlighted in Table 6 of Chapter 4, it is expected that the target KPI of engaging 770 citizens will be exceeded.

With regards to the progress made at each pilot for recruiting participants for the ACCEPT project, Table 7 compares the target number of citizens to the results from the ex-ante survey. Results show that Greece and Spain have made excellent progress with 95% and 88%, respectively, of those that responded to the ex-ante level survey being eligible to participate in ACCEPT. The eligibility rate is slightly lower for Switzerland at 61% and relatively low for the Netherlands 33%. However, this low rate is due to the potential participant's eligibility based on the technical requirements needed to be part of ACCEPT. Reaching out to potential participants has not been an issue given that all partners are over 74% of the target number of citizens to be reached. A continuation of the communication and engagement activities described throughout this deliverable should result in all pilots meeting their respective citizen recruitment targets, and the engagement targets of the ACCEPT project overall.

Table 7. Comparison of citizen recruitment goals with ex-ante survey results

Pilot site	Recruitment target (number of citizens)	Ex-ante respondents (eligible)	Percentage of target achieved (eligible)
Greece	64	61 (61)	95% (95%)
Spain	50	55 (44)	100% (88%)
Netherlands	51	40 (17)	78% (33%)
Switzerland	86	64 (52)	74% (61%)

Note: The eligibility figures in brackets represent the citizens which have been deemed eligible to take part at a high level based on the results of the first level of the ex-ante survey in T6.1

In addition to the targets for citizen recruitment, the engagement activities undertaken at the four pilot sites has contributed to the targets related to the LL activities in T3.1 (see Table 8). With regards to the quantitative targets, it is expected that 1000 stakeholders will be engaged as part of the co-creation process and 16 workshops (4 per demo site) will be held during the project lifespan. As specified in this report, 353 citizens have been engaged in the recruitment activities, and 2 workshops have been held, one in the Greek pilot and one in the Swiss pilot region. In addition to these quantitative targets, the various engagements described in the previous chapters have facilitated important LL aspects such as building trust with communities and receiving feedback on concepts for co-creation.

Table 8. KPIs related to the Living Lab activities

Category	KPI	Metric	Target
Co-creation / feedback loops/ UX	Co-creation participation	Stakeholders participating in co-creation process	1000
	Co-creation participation	Workshops for stakeholder engagement	16 (4 per demo site)
Engagement	Stakeholder engagement	Engaging citizens in the demonstration activities	770
		Engaging stakeholders in the co-creation process	1000